

The Digital Media Revolution – Historic Towns Atlases (HTAs) in a Data-Driven World

For my parents
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Media and Revolutions

Over the last few decades, the world of knowledge has changed dramatically. Digital information is ever more present in modern-day culture as well as in current research, and nothing short of a media revolution is taking place.¹ Media revolutions – like any other revolution – turn over conditions previously perceived as given and, more often than not, unchangeable while setting free enormous energies. These energies can be constructive as well as destructive, and often are both at the same time. Media revolutions in particular pertain to the production, distribution, and consumption of knowledge, usually making these processes faster, easier, and more efficient.

The late medieval transition in book production – from the manuscripts of monastic scribes to the printing press of the late medieval book market – may serve as a prominent example to illustrate the potential of media revolutions: When this particular media revolution was in full swing and books produced in more efficient ways, i.e. by combining the printing press with another technological innovation – movable types –, the written word became accessible to wider audiences. By distributing knowledge on a new scale, the advent of the printing press brought enormous changes to pre-modern European societies when it served as midwife to Reformation and Enlightenment. Adding an ominous note to this success story: While book printing also became a commercial enterprise on a new scale, not all the existing manuscript books were rendered in print to enjoy a wider circulation. Processes of selection came into play and, as in any media revolution, knowledge itself was affected in fundamental ways. Even in the 15th and 16th centuries, the question of which books promised to make a profit in the market introduced a powerful filter and determined what texts actually were to see a print edition. So while some works suddenly enjoyed a wide circulation and new audiences, this filter mechanism sentenced thousands of others which before were deemed useful and worth copying to oblivion. By what has been said so far is implied that the success of any publication in the print world by no means guarantees its survival of a media revolution. Indeed, there is no reason to believe that the current one – the transition from analogous to digital media – should be any more lenient to those who do not heed its call, adapt to necessities arising, and prove their continuous usefulness, than the preceding ones.

The project frequently referred to as ‘the European Historic Towns Atlas’ is, in fact, a conglomerate of self-funded projects in twenty individual European countries ranging geographically from Ireland to Romania and from Iceland to Italy.² Some of these have been producing printed Historic Towns Atlases (HTAs) for 50 years now.³ The atlases provide

1 Thinking about the current situation of the Historic Towns Atlases as well as a suitable narrative form I have drawn much inspiration from Giesecke, *Von den Mythen der Buchkultur*, and the wonderful study by Hellinga, *Caxton in Focus*. Many thanks to the editors of this volume for their patience, also to Kristin Steiner, Münster, for her support with the preparation of the manuscript.

2 See the interactive distribution map: <https://www.uni-muenster.de/Staedtegeschichte/en/portal/staedteatlanten/karte.html> (accessed 18.01.2021).

3 For accounts on the history of the European Project, see the introductory parts of Ehbrecht, *Städteatlanten*; Clarke & Simms, *Lords and Towns*; Czaja, Noga, Opll & Scheutz (eds.), *Political Functions*.

researchers and the public with comparable cartographic source material, mainly historic maps and town plans, giving unique insights into the layout, built-up area and surroundings of European towns throughout their history. With over 600 HTAs published and counting, the atlases allow for a unique access to the history of European urbanism and can be called but a great success. New projects are still being added to the general scheme and those dormant for some reason or other re-activated.⁴ The undoubted strength of HTAs is the close look into the topographical history of each individual town and the abundance of cartographic material offered by the fascicles. The maps as well as the sheer amount of textual information that more often than not rivals a standard monograph on a town's history are a treasure trove for anyone interested in one particular town.

Covering individual towns, each HTA is a popular publication among local history enthusiasts and in this context, their usefulness for exploring the topographical history of each town covered is not to be denied. Yet, in academic urban studies and comparative research on a larger scale the HTAs have so far made less of an impact than the initiators of the atlas scheme had hoped for.⁵ Although important inroads have been made to address research questions from within, outside the specialist scientific community the HTA material tends to be neglected. In part this was caused by a shift in the mainstream research interests away from matters regarding 'space' as a research topic in the second half of the 20th century. Signs have improved with the arrival in the 1990s of the Spatial Turn in the Humanities, the increased research interest in the role of spatial practices for human culture(s).⁶ Yet, in this field, methodologies and questions have become dominant which again led historians to ignoring the map evidence and topographical information rendered by the HTAs, the theoretical basis of which was largely perceived as rooted in the first half of the 20th century. Enormous benefits could be gained by systematically combining archaeological and cartographic evidence – the one being restricted to excavation sites but assigning exact dates to structures uncovered, the other potentially putting these in their townscape context but without being able to date with any precision of itself. Yet, the disciplines so akin in their objectives keep drifting apart and with few instances of combined forces each sticks to their methodologies leaving possible synergies unused, much to the disadvantage of urban studies in general and the HTA community in particular.⁷ For these reasons, the question how the HTAs may come to terms with the challenges posed by the digital media revolution is an important one. The opportunities for making their voices heard

4 For general information see the web portal created by the Institute for Comparative Urban History (Institut für vergleichende Städtegeschichte, Münster – IStG): <https://www.uni-muenster.de/Staedtegeschichte/en/portal/staedteatlanten/index.html> (accessed 21.01.2025), and the homepage of the International Commission for the History of Towns: <https://www.historiaurbium.org/activities/historic-towns-atlases/atlas-working-group/> (accessed 21.01.2025).

5 Gearty & Simms, European Historic Towns Atlas project. The first way of unlocking this vast material follows a typological approach attributing each of the already published HTAs to a town type, the other takes a closer look at the output of two regional HTAs and one type of town asking what kind of source material they have in store and what kinds of comparative questions may be asked on its account (see Czaja, Noga, Opll & Scheutz (eds.), *Political Functions*, especially Szende & Szilágyi, *Town Typology*, and Stracke, *Industrial Towns*). Such attempts, however, are set in a time in which map use in historical, archaeological and geographical research is in decline. For the moment, it is important to note that trends in research methodology and epistemology are important factors regarding the use of source material, because there is a chance that the tide may turn.

6 Döring, *Spatial Turn*.

7 Important attempts at revitalising the interdisciplinary dialogue ought not to go unmentioned: Opll, *Stadtgründung*; Igel, *Wandel der Stadt*.

in a renewed interdisciplinary dialogue about past urban spaces based on a common digital methodology have never been as good. Yet, it is necessary to understand how the digital media revolution affects the atlas work and spatial research in order to realise the full potential of the HTAs in future academic discourse. This is to be explored in the following paragraphs.

The ‘Manuscript Stage’ of HTA production – Diversity as a problem?

When the first HTA projects started producing atlases in the late 1960s and 1970s, the cartographer’s task was not unlike that of the medieval scribe’s: drawing maps by hand meant that well-trained professionals performed a skilled manual labour that required a very high artistic level. Even the steel pens used back then still very much resembled medieval quills and the maps were printed on the modern descendant of the self-same apparatus used by Gutenberg, Caxton, and other 15th century printing pioneers. For the professional cartographers employed in the IStG, the switch to the computer and digital drawing software for their work in the 1990s certainly was the one step at which the digital media revolution was most obviously and intensely felt. But even then, the output was still primarily the regular HTAs that by their nature as print publications were completed once the ink was dry. This was also the point in time at which the information published could no longer be augmented, unless a copy was annotated for printing a second edition at some later point in time. Hence, digital data created in the process was after some time considered useless and eventually deleted, the printed maps being the exclusive product.

Looking back now on the long history of the European Historic Towns Atlas, an obvious characteristic in the HTA projects’ output is diversity. The differences between the national and regional publication series concern the content of the fascicles as a whole, the number and types of historic maps they feature, the editorial treatment of the maps as well as the inclusion of thematic maps, of an interpretative text, and of a text-based gazetteer of topographic information. Articles and reviews assessing the publications of the European HTAs in a more general sense and with comparison in mind invariably take note of the more obvious variations in the cartographic material.⁸ For our purposes, though, it is useful to focus on the one map in particular which is central to the whole HTA idea: the 1:2,500 Main Map.

For studying past urban spaces, the cartographic sources of the first exact survey maps (*Kataster, cadastre, Ordnance Survey* etc.) produced by the evolving modern nation states from the 1820s onwards, generally for land taxation, are an ideal tool. They combine the benefits of geometrical exactness, richness in detail, and of pre-dating the immense transformations the industrialisation had inflicted upon the urban fabric almost everywhere. However, any historian who visits the archives to use this material invariably hits a brick wall: scattered archival records, a multitude of maps in different scales as well as large, unwieldy formats are just the more prominent problems the original cartographic evidence has in stock for the user. Moreover, the underlying idea of a largely uniform cartographic record throughout Europe was not based on broad empirical knowledge.⁹ In fact, anything but uniformity is to be found in the remains of early cartographic surveys across Europe.¹⁰ Variations in the taxation systems of the

8 Conzen, *Retrieving the pre-industrial built environments*. Others ought to be mentioned, but Conzen’s review is perhaps the most comprehensive and also the voice of a scholar not directly involved with the HTA production.

9 In lieu of the forthcoming volume concerning the 19th century of the seminal handbook Harley & Woodward, *The History*, see: Baigent & Kain, *The cadastral Map*. See, more specifically: Clarke & Gearty, *Sources*, esp. 14–19, and the section “Quellenkritische Bemerkungen zu einzelnen Tafeln“ in each volume of Johaneck, et. al. (eds.), *Deutscher Historischer Städteatlas*.

10 The differences are explicable by territorial boundaries and mapping traditions of the early 19th century. By these coincidences records in former Prussian territories in eastern Germany

territorial and national states, but also in surveying and mapping methods, and a timespan of close to a century between the first surveys account for a degree of variation initially underestimated. When the basic scheme for the HTAs was developed to amend this situation, the HTA Main Map was conceived of as a redrawing of the historic survey maps. The plans cover the historic town centre and its immediate vicinity were piecing together and reduced to the scale of 1:2,500. The redrawing plot by plot of the original cartographic image produced snapshots of historic townscapes, large-scale plot plans of the inner city that are the most important component of each HTA. The Main Map has sufficient detail to serve as a basis for any retrogressive reconstruction of the urban environment of earlier times and for the sequential analysis of the town's initial layout and development. For such studies, earlier maps and other forms of evidence such as written sources or archaeological excavations need to be taken into account to which the 19th century town plans are a genuine and valuable complement.

While there are many other types of maps and other material included in the HTAs, the edition of the 19th century survey maps is the one entity to primarily achieve the main goal of the HTAs: to provide maps with the same specifications to allow for detailed analysis not only of the urban fabric of an individual town, but to enable comparative studies in the development of, and the interdependencies within, the European urban network; this is to eventually lead to a better understanding of the complex and unique research object of European urbanism (*Städtewesen*). In order to better understand the data issues involved with this kind of evidence, it is useful to first conduct a retrospective comparison of cartographic concepts used for the Main Maps edited in the HTAs; this has been done for twenty atlases, each from a different regional or national European HTA project.¹¹ Based on this sample and the cartographic differences found, five different editorial approaches to constructing the Main Map can be seen (cf fig. 1 a–e):

and Poland resemble each other more closely than in Eastern and Western Germany. Concerning Variations within Poland, see Czaja & Golba, *Städteatlanten und GIS*, 54. The HTA project work in many regions instigated the first attempts to take stock of the cartographic sources available in the archives and record offices.

11 Rhenish HTA (Milz, *Rheinischer Städteatlas XV*, 83/ IV, 21); Austrian HTA (Pühringer, *Österreichischer Städteatlas X: Waidhofen an der Taya*); Croatian HTA (Slukan Altić, *Povijesni atlas gradova / Historischer Städteatlas von Kroatien 5: Varaždin*); Swiss HTA (Fuchs, *Historischer Städteatlas der Schweiz: Chur*); Belgian HTA (Debaere, *Atlas Historique des Villes Belges / Historische Stedenatlas van België, Vlaanderen: Masseik*); Scandinavian HTA/Sweden (Ericsson & Hall, *Scandinavian Atlas of Historic Towns 8 Sweden: Falun*); Romanian HTA (Niedermaier, *Atlas istorical oraşelor din România / Städtegeschichteatlas Rumäniens A, 1: Suceava/Suczawa*); Scandinavian HTA/Finland: (Hietala (ed.), *Scandinavian Atlas of Historic Towns: N.S. 2 Suomi-Finland: Helsinki*); Czech HTA (Šmahel (ed.), *Historický atlas měst České republiky/ Historischer Städteatlas der Tschechischen Republik 23: Kadaň/ Kaden*); Ukrainian HTA (Kapral (ed.), *Ukrainian Historic Town Atlas I: Lviv*); Dutch HTA (Herwijnen, van (ed.), *Historische Stedenatlas van Nederland 7: Bergen op Zoom*); French HTA (Bidot-Germa, Devos & Juliat, *Atlas historique des villes de France 51: Pau*); Italian HTA (G. Sassatelli, C. Morigi Govi, J. Ortalli & F. Bocchi (curatore), *Atlante storico delle Città Italiane Emilia Romagna I: Bologna*); German HTA (Daniel Stracke et. al., *Deutscher Historischer Städteatlas 5: Dortmund*); Westphalian HTA (Ehbrecht et. al., *Historischer Atlas westfälischer Städte 7: Soest*); British HTA (Addyman et al. (ed.), *British Historic Towns Atlas 5: York*); Polish HTA (Barciak et. al., *Atlas Historyczny Miast Polskich / The Historical Atlas of Polish Towns IV Śląsk/ Schlesien, 15 : Gliwice*); Irish HTA (Kelly & O'Keeffe, *Irish Historic Towns Atlas 27*); Hessian HTA (Holger Th. Gräf, *Hessischer Städteatlas 3,2: Bad Orb*); Hungarian HTA (András Kubinyi (ed.), *Magyar Várostarténeti Atlas/ Hungarian atlas of historic towns 1: Sopron*).

fig. 1 a: Lobel model multi-period map style

fig. 1 b: Stob model source edition style

fig. 1 c: Reduced content map style

fig. 1 d: Multiple maps style

fig. 1 e: Reproduced map

Lobel model multi-period maps: The British HTA project, initialised by Mary D. Lobel, co-founder of the HTA European scheme, was met with complicated circumstances: an early onset of the industrial revolution in the British Isles made for early transformations of urban form, on the one hand, and the British Ordnance Survey starting to produce large-scale maps in 1842, for comparatively late cartographic sources, on the other.¹² The Main Map solution found to amend this situation was later termed ‘multi-period maps’. This type of map combines the redrawing of the original Ordnance Survey map as a base map with topographic features superimposed from earlier periods not depicted in the original cartographic sources. Such features, like buildings demolished before the survey, convey an idea of how those particular urban spaces were transformed over time. The British Lobel model of the multi-period map was adopted by other projects in continental Western Europe and Italy,¹³ partly with slight variations such as the addition of information on cartographic sources and contour lines.

Stoob model source edition: The Main Map model most HTA projects have resorted to is the one developed and propagated by IStG founder and historian Heinz Stoob.¹⁴ The Stoob model

12 The British HTA was initialised by general editor Lobel et. al. (eds.), *Historic Towns* (subsequently as: *The Atlas of Historic Towns*, *The British Atlas of Historic Towns*, *The British Historic Towns Atlas*).

13 The French HTA, the Dutch HTA, and the Italian HTA.

14 Stoob initialised the German national and the Westphalian regional HTA projects: Stoob et. al. (eds.), *Deutscher Städteatlas* (later continued as *Deutscher Historischer Städteatlas*);

comprises the original lines as given in the cadastral sources (without later alterations) representing the town layout and employs colours to signify the land-use. The basic approach of the Stob model in itself has been varied, mainly by adding further information¹⁵ some of which derives from the cadastral sources. Based on the assumption that property boundaries are a feature of the urban landscape that is more stable than buildings or land-use types, some cartographic editors mark the plot boundaries by a slightly thicker line to indicate their different value as a clue for the morpho-genetic interpretation. Also, cadastral sections' boundaries (*Flurstücksgrenzen*) may be introduced to give a direct reference to the historic maps used as sources. Moreover, Stob model Main Maps vary in the textual information given, street names and field names, for example. Also, numeration systems may be included in the maps, such as cadastral numbers referencing plots and tax information in the written sources, or house numbers. Some projects also infuse their maps with additional cartographic information such as contour lines that convey information on the elevation of the terrain. All of these additions are to enhance the interpretation of the town layout on the basis of the historic cadastral sources, much like one would expect to be aided by an editor's comment in a critical edition of a written text. Stob was adamant to separate the cartographic source edition from additional historical information pertaining to buildings, structures or the morpho-genesis of the town. This way, the redrawn map is open to changing interpretations that are depicted in separate developmental maps.¹⁶

Reduced content map: A few HTA projects have not produced a regular Stob model map, but due to editorial decisions or the lack of suitable sources, only print reduced versions with varying content.¹⁷ The reduction in cartographic elements like the colours or symbology, omitting of most or all textual information, and the inclusion of only the urban kernel within the limits of the former town walls without any of the surrounding landscape account for a loss of information and problems of orientation.

Multiple maps: Colour is an important and palpable means for conveying spatial information about areal objects and their properties. Where maps are not printed in colour but rendered in shades of grey, additional symbols may have to be used as a vehicle for this information. In order to not overload the map image, HTA projects have found the solution to distribute the information by category on more than one map using the same cadastral base map and scale.¹⁸ Although in comparison the visual difference to the products of other HTA projects is largest here, this pragmatic, cost-cutting procedure does not automatically mean a lack of information. In fact, even more information such as plot boundaries may be supplied, which feature only in a minority of the Stob model Main Maps. Only the presentation of the information is quite different and a synopsis of map elements more difficult although the superimposition of grid lines may help with the orientation.

Reproduced maps: Most HTA projects redraw the cadastral map as is the standard procedure, i.e. cartographers trace lines from the originals' scans using an appropriate software and, thus, create a clear (vectorised) image of the townscape. There are, however, also those projects that, given suitable source material, take the shortcut of using a single clean copy of the

Stob et. al. (eds.), *Westfälischer Städteatlas* (later continued as *Historischer Atlas westfälischer Städte*). The title 'Stob model' is borrowed from Clarke, *Joining the Club*.

15 Such as (cadastral) numbers, field names, street names, plot boundaries, cadastral boundaries, (historic/modern) contour lines, grid lines, colours.

16 Following the Stob model are the German HTA, Westfalian HTA, Rhenish HTA, Hessian HTA (except Brandenburgischer Städteatlas), Polish HTA, Austrian HTA, Hungarian HTA, Croatian HTA, and Irish HTA.

17 Swiss HTA, Belgian HTA, and the German regional Brandenburg HTA.

18 Thus practiced in the older Scandinavian HTAs (except recent Finnish volumes) and the Romanian HTA.

cadastral map (e.g. from the Habsburg *Franzischeischer Kataster*) and only provide a scanned raster image, thus resorting to a facsimile approach in cartographic source edition.¹⁹ While the standard scale of 1:2,500 is generally accepted and mostly delivered in the printed HTAs, projects reproducing a scanned map in facsimile style sometimes retain the original scale of their sources, in the case of the *Franzischeischer Kataster* 1:2,880. As this approach leaves the originals largely untreated, there is further variation where the sources differ.

The diversity in map content and visual styles encountered in the sample seems to not aid but hinder attempts at comparatively studying pre-modern townscapes using the 1:2,500 Main Maps from different HTA projects.²⁰ However, differences in mapping approaches do not automatically obliterate comparison per se: in a comparative setting, the trained eye can work around different shades of colour and even different cartographic symbologies without too much difficulty. Yet, the differences between the print maps are considerable and not restricted to style or visual appearance; the maps vary in content, and this is where differences can severely limit the range of possible comparisons to be conducted. Moreover, for the cartographer, scale and content are interconnected variables: the scale directly influences the degree of generalisation applied, i.e. the smaller the scale of a map, the fewer details it will include so as to retain its legibility. Geometric shapes in smaller-scale maps are simplified or substituted by symbols, map objects too small to be depicted are left out entirely. The question which mapping differences are problematic is entirely dependent on the research questions. While a Stooß model map may allow for the synopsis of a town's ground plan with contour lines to study how the street network was laid out in order to negotiate a steep rise of the terrain, comparisons of this kind are not possible when Main Maps feature no contour lines at all, naturally. In the second best scenario, contour information may be provided by a different map in the same HTA, but variations in scale and detail then also add difficulties for the user. Given this state of the art, HTA Main Maps show most similarities when they are produced according to the same basic model. The fact remains, therefore, that map-based comparative studies may find more fertile ground in the common traits of maps in insular and Western Europe with Italy where the Lobel model is followed (excepting Ireland), on the one hand, and in Central and Eastern Europe (adding Ireland) where the Stooß model and its variants are most popular, on the other (**fig. 2**). In order to create perfectly comparable maps, the HTA projects would have to overcome their colourful diversity, but for the printed HTAs this would be an unlikely breach of individual practices and the cartographic conventions of long-running series. The question of common mapping standards was raised in the ICHT Atlas Working Group, but no consent was reached and no serious attempt made to overcome localised traditions in favour of a unified concept. Moreover, as digitalisation transcended all aspects of society and research, the HTA projects made a dash towards a new goal, i.e. to produce digital content – and with the issue of standardisation unresolved, the diversity of the printed maps also started to seep into the digital sphere.

19 See Czech HTA and Ukrainian HTA, but also Finnish HTA.

20 The lack of a theoretical framework of research goals and a clear-cut methodology to formulate questions and address issues of comparison so as to allow for a deeper understanding of European towns, although weighty explorative and theoretical work has recently been conducted to that effect; see especially Clarke & Simms, *Lords and Towns*; Czaja, Noga, Opll & Scheutz (eds.), *Political Functions*.

fig. 2: Distribution of map styles used in Historic Towns Atlases

‘Digital Inkunabula’ – PDF files and interactive maps online

Today we know that the printing press in its medieval beginnings was used without realising the full potential of this new technology for the production of books: On the outset, the text for each individual page of a book used to be carved from a single block of wood. Once this was accomplished, each wooden block was used to print the same page over, until it fell apart – which happened rather quickly. Needless to say, these early ‘blockbooks’ are now interesting curiosities, but they were tedious to produce, not efficient on the available resources and the blocks not re-usable in a sustainable way. The use of the term media ‘revolution’ – with its connotation of ‘an event’ – tends to obliterate the fact that the positive potential of new media can only be realised by a process of adaptation. This involves the acquisition of new technological knowhow as well an understanding of its theoretical basis and more general implications. Until this was achieved in the late Middle Ages, blockbooks were the best thing to be produced, although they did not make much of an impact in the scholarly, let alone everyday culture of their time. Much the same is true for the earlier digital efforts put up by the

HTA community; this is not meant to belittle the pioneering efforts that have been made, as they all need to be regarded as necessary steps along the way.²¹

The HTA projects' progression to publishing digital content started in the 1990s when CD-ROMs appeared to be the media best suited for this purpose. Before long, information was increasingly sought on the internet and digitised copies of books were becoming the norm even with historians (who are by their very calling of a bibliophilic disposition). Because the print atlases were available in bulk only in a handful of specialised libraries,²² the idea took root that the world-wide web would be the most efficient way to make a better public and scientific impact and so the HTA projects naturally strove to present their work online. Although it is relatively easy to put the HTAs online for inspection in a conventional viewing application or as a downloadable file, as easy as it is to set up a project website, not all HTA projects, even the most active ones, have done so.²³ Challenges remain, and these are not technical issues in the first place, but concern the workload and, even more importantly, involve copyrights. If publishing houses are involved with the HTA production, on the other hand, the decision to go online with the atlases may not be governed by research interests at all, but by financial ones. This is a problem in particular when publishing contracts predate the digital media revolution. Even when projects go online, and the digital presentation of the HTAs is accessible via a common web portal, content, visualisation, and data formats are very different.

An attractive way to present HTA content online is by making maps and texts available as PDF files. Suitable for download and allowing for small file sizes if derived from vector graphic originals, PDFs are the closest thing to a print atlas in the digital sphere. As PDFs are also the exchange format commonly used for digital printing, there is a range of options to pursue – from big-sized 'print originals' down to files of reduced resolution or water-marked versions that may help avoid piracy by reprint. Due to the possibilities and broad-range compatibility they offer, PDFs are a viable choice and recommended by the Atlas Working Group of the International Commission for the History of Towns as a preferable way to digital HTA content. This approach has been used extensively by the British Historic Towns Trust, for example, uploading content from the British HTA.²⁴ Some other projects, though, were looking for the *new* possibilities that the digital "new media" had to offer. Next to solving the availability issue, the idea of creating interactive maps was the second major pull factor for HTA projects to develop digital content. The Austrian HTA (*Österreichischer Städteatlas*) has diverged from the straightforward PDF path with an obvious benefit: The online atlas – for the whole series has been digitised with great care²⁵ – allows to search for individual topographical features and

21 The ICHT Atlas Working Group is gaining in understanding and technical knowledge. Considerable movement can be seen in the Digital Initiative Group Workshops: Budapest 2012: Digitisation, Interactive Maps; Dublin 2014: Developing historic towns atlases for the future; Leicester 2015: The British Historic Towns Atlas 'Digital Futures' Workshop; Münster 2017: GIS-based Cartography – a Change of Media or a Change of Paradigms?; Dublin 2018: The 1:2.500 base map of HTAs and the prospects of digital edition. See also Chodějovská, Gearty & Stracke, "Digital Turn".

22 At the Institut für vergleichende Städtegeschichte / Institute for Comparative Urban History (IStG) in Münster, for example.

23 The interactive distribution map (<https://www.uni-muenster.de/Staedtegeschichte/en/portal/staedteatlanten/karte.html> [accessed 21.01.2025]) features links to project websites and online content of all HTA projects, as far as available.

24 <https://www.historictownstrust.uk/atlas> (accessed 21.01.2025). Click on "Towns" to access PDF files.

25 <https://www.arcanum.hu/hu/online-kiadvanyok/OsterreichischerStadtatlas-osterreichischer-stadteatlas-1/> (Note: When accessed on 21.01.2025, the interactive functionality was discontinued).

for comparing the historic maps with the modern topography (Open Street Map). This adds another set of information to the presentation and a transparency function provides an additional advantage compared with the print version. In its own digital approach, the German national HTA project (*Deutscher Historischer Städteatlas*) tries to capitalise on its main strength and that is the considerable number of redrawn historic and thematic maps.²⁶ On the basis of these vector graphics, HTML-based web modules with interactive features are created which provide an intuitive functionality allowing the user to choose from several layers of information in order to create his or her own maps from the content given.²⁷ Both examples add new perspectives to the material and provide a framework for the presentation of the digital atlas content.

There is a need for the work of the HTA projects to be published in an accessible, digital format. The towns of Europe are a unique form of settlement and cultural heritage. Their urban landscapes have evolved over centuries and understanding the formation and transformation of urban spaces through time, how local history and urban form interconnect with European developments at large, is of interest to the general public. Retracing and comparing the topographical history of towns reveals commonalities and diversity in the European settlement structure and pinpoints characteristics of European culture. This is where PDF and HTML publications based on the HTAs have an important function to fulfil. All these solutions for presenting map content online, however, suffer from one major flaw: They cannot be adjusted in order to solve research questions restricting researchers to a purely visual analyses of the maps. Even where interactive maps allow the information to be filtered, there is but a pre-set number of layers that may be viewed. All information is stored in a rigid system and may be visualised only in the specific way the online map module was designed to. Moreover, the diversity we have encountered in the print atlases is being transferred one-to-one to the digital publications together with all their problems and limitations. While basic manipulation of the map image is possible, because even 'static' PDFs allow to pan and zoom in/out, the interactive maps especially make it difficult to share information. A limited graphics saving option may be used by means of a 'screen shot', but HTML-based web modules have no download function. Even the most sophisticated 3D reconstruction produced on the basis of HTA data that gives a 'realistic' impression of the layout, proportions, and appearance of a town in the Middle Ages to walk through, would be liable to the same shortcomings.

Hence, it can be argued with some justification that in spite of their benefits none of these online solutions fulfil in the digital sphere the initial aim for which the print HTAs have once been called to life, i.e. to allow for analytical and comparative research. Research practices and methodologies, however, have changed in fundamental ways: Map analysis is no longer being conducted solely in the visual sphere, a change that has been caused by the advent of Geographic Information Systems (GIS). In the 1980s, remarkable pioneering work for the HTA community was undertaken in Italy.²⁸ Based on taxation and cadastral sources from the Middle Ages onwards in an embryonic GIS, the computer was used to aid historical spatial analyses. Yet, the technological state-of-the-art and limited financial means put heavy constraints on the scope and results of this kind of research. Back then, these interesting attempts have not been followed up in the rest of the European HTA community and despite the superior methods of data analysis, the published final result was still a printed map.

The Atlas Working Group of the International Commission for the History of Towns (ICHT) has initially regarded the challenge of the digital age as primarily one of making available the printed atlases in a digital form and publish HTAs not only in print but also on the internet.

26 For compilations of thematic maps, see Stracke & Tippach, *Der Deutsche Historische Städteatlas*, esp. 71–76; Stracke, *Industrial Towns*.

27 <https://www.uni-muenster.de/Staedtegeschichte/portal/Stadtkarten/index.html> (accessed 21.01.2025).

28 Bocchi & Lugli, *Computer methods*; see also Biget, Hervé & Thébert, *Les Cadastres*.

However, putting the HTAs online is not what the *digital challenge* really is about. Neither is it about using a more advanced software to produce the same print atlases nor even to carry out better analyses and then print more sophisticated maps. Just like the print HTAs in the beginning, the digital work on the atlases needs to aim higher than just the atlases themselves and instead focus on the question of how it can best support comparative urban research – only now this means research using digital tools. Thus, the digital challenge is to conduct basic research and provide raw data for analysis which is open to interpretation and also available for re-interpretation at a later time with new methods yet to be developed. This research data needs to adhere to transparent scientific standards revealing the origins and quality of the sources as well as the methods of their treatment and of data production. It also includes finding solutions for the exchange of data among researchers across academic boundaries so as to involve of all academic fields dealing in historical spatial research. Else, there is a danger in producing digital blockbooks and online incunabula.

Gutenberg 2.0 – GIS and the Data-Driven Approach

For the projects combining to form the European Historic Towns Atlas, the new technology to master in the digital media revolution – the equivalent to the addition of movable types to the printing press – are Geographic Information Systems (GIS).²⁹ Having been around in geoscience since the late 1960s, GIS is by no means a new tool. However, since calculating and storage capabilities of personal computers have improved on a massive scale, powerful Open Source software is freely available, and the ubiquitous internet can handle data transfers of enormous proportions, they have become a perfect fit for researchers investigating urban spaces. Recent years have seen important progress in software development both in proprietary systems (e.g. ESRI ArcGIS) as well as open source applications (e.g. QuantumGIS/QGIS)³⁰, so that the argument “GIS is expensive” no longer holds.

GIS combine digital mapping and database functions that endow historic maps with real-world coordinates so that every point on the map refers unambiguously to a physical location on the earth’s surface. Items depicted in historic maps can be modelled as digital geofeatures (geometric data) and linked to further information stored in the geodatabase (attribute data). GIS combine these datatypes with a set of powerful analytical functions: Accessing the geometric data, the system allows for areal measurements and distance calculations between the mapped geofeatures so that studies of town layout are simpler and – depending on the input data³¹ – more exact than manual methods in traditional metrology. Thus, they are an ideal tool for the analysis of urban spaces in the past using data derived from the survey maps of 19th century cadastres. Combined and processed, these cartographic sources reveal the layout of a town ready for the synchronous analysis of its morphological structure and spatial development. The maps edited by the HTA projects also yield information on former buildings, land use, and infrastructure to be stored as attribute data, analysed and visualised. Statistical analysis is enabled and further GIS functions (‘merging’) allow for the analytic combination of different data sets. Past urban spaces as they appear in the georeferenced historical maps can be directly related to the modern townscape in a very exact way to show processes of historical change, of expansion and densification.

29 For a ‘gentle introduction’ see: https://docs.qgis.org/3.16/en/docs/gentle_gis_introduction/ (accessed 21.02.2025); the multitude of introductory volumes and handbooks as well as online content, treating all aspects relating to GIS, geodata production, and spatial analysis makes it superfluous to mention any specific work, here.

30 <https://qgis.org/en/site/forusers/download.html> (accessed 21.02.2025).

31 Lilley, Mapping and analysing, stresses the importance of accurate measurements and recommends resurveying via GPS for more exact results.

Several HTA projects already employ GIS, and have gathered useful experiences. Those spearheading this development have found that there are differences for a cartographer between the ‘traditional’ work of drawing a map by using drawing software and producing geodata in GIS. In the first instance, both processes produce digital data that are to be the basis for print atlases; in this capacity and on this level, none of the programmes may justly be called superior to the other.³² On the practical level, GIS skills and knowhow are unevenly distributed among the community and there are many open questions pertaining to, for example, the right software solutions and the development of best practices for a streamlined GIS-based HTA workflow. On the theoretical side, there is a need to understand the scientific implications of this change of technology as it touches upon the very epistemology and methodology of topographical research. For GIS subject the historical cartographic evidence to transformative procedures, i.e. georeferencing/georectification. The use of different geographic reference systems may distort a map image in ways some historians regard as contrary to editorial principles. As ever so often, practical and theoretical issues are two sides of the same coin. The choice for a technical solution and the ways in which data is being processed affects the information to be transported, the scope of the research, and the quality of results we may expect. Hence, there are neither trivial problems nor straightforward answers, and rarely will solutions be found by either the “researchers” or the “technicians” on their own, but only in collaboration and dialogue.

What sounds like a complication for the atlas work is, in fact, the best opportunity to overcome most of the problematic diversity in the printed HTA Base Maps we have seen above. In the GIS-based data-driven approach, the differences in style are utterly unimportant, simply because each new map generated from a particular dataset can be styled and restyled. The same shade of green to signify vegetable gardens in two maps is easily achieved by tweaking the colour values. This way, an HTA project used to producing print maps according to the Stoob model may choose, for instance, to print the next one in the tradition of a different model (**cf. fig. 2**). In the data-driven GIS approach, map scales can be adjusted, colour schemes and symbology varied, and content added, subtracted, or changed. The GIS attribute table or spatial database can be filled with historical information pertaining to individual historic buildings and landscape features. The decision to publish this information from the geodata base as a printed gazetteer (like in the Irish, Rhenish, or Hungarian HTAs) or in the form of a growth phases map (as is customary in the German national HTA) – that’s entirely up to the data user. But map style is not the only difference between the printed Main Maps as we have seen: map content may also be affected. For example, not all HTA projects choose to supply contour lines, because they lack the people power necessary for digitising them, have no access to the relevant sources, or because they regard such information as dispensable to their scheme. While with the print maps comparison ends here, this is not the final step of the data-driven journey. A researcher looking to compare the influence of the landscape’s elevation on the street layout of towns will not be deterred by this missing bit of information, but use the basic geometric data to save months of project time and only add contour data to the existing data sets. For GIS allow the database to be expanded and replenished with further information and this is where perhaps their greatest benefit comes into play: the combination of geodata from various sources in one system. With any luck, that researcher may not only benefit from the historic cadastral data supplied by HTA projects, but acquire ready-made elevation data from a surveying office.

32 For all digitisation aspects also see Lilley, *Mapping Futures?*. The software MAPublisher, mentioned by Lilley (p. 286) is an asset to the project ‘Deutscher Historischer Städteatlas’. As a plug-in for Adobe Illustrator it constitutes the missing link between GIS and ‘traditional’ drawing software (<https://www.avenza.com/mapublisher/> [accessed 21.02.2025]).

The principle of data combination was successfully put to the trial in a 2020 Summer School³³ using geodata produced in the project *Deutscher Historischer Städteatlas* (German Historic Towns Atlas) for the town of Mühlhausen in Thuringia. Information on the professions and tax amounts of Mühlhausen's citizens was harvested from late medieval tax registers, transcribed by eager students³⁴ and added to the geodata sets derived from the 19th century cadastral survey, the precious 'leftovers' from producing the 1:2,500 Main Map in the print version of the atlas.³⁵ In addition to advanced paleographic skills and the working methods of social topography, the students learned data collection procedures and were introduced to basic digital spatial analysis using the Geoinformation System QGIS. The interpretation of the data naturally required the historian's traditional mindset and source criticism and the combination of data allowed for new and interesting insights into the structure of social spaces in this late medieval imperial town.³⁶ However, much more important are the implications of this principle for the future impact of the HTA work in research. For GIS have become a standard in spatial data analysis in many academic fields, especially the various disciplines dedicated to understanding past urban landscapes, such as Archaeology, Geography, and Urban Morphology due to their immense potential to solve a great variety of research questions. By now, the capabilities of combining data make GIS a likely methodological bridge between these disciplines that, more often than not, have long studied urban spaces largely on the slim basis of "their own" source material – cartographic sources *or* material remains. However, as long as data is georeferenced and provided in compatible formats, variety is the forte of GIS technology. The integration of different forms of evidence is bound to unleash their immense potential for solving research questions.³⁷

Significant advances in topographical research are to be expected when the most detailed form of historic cartographic evidence, the HTAs' 19th century survey maps are being processed by the most powerful and universally used tool of analysis, GIS. Moreover, GIS link the maps provided by HTAs to other types of data paving the way towards interdisciplinary urban studies. The newly emerging academic fields such as Digital Humanities and Digital History have initialised a debate not only on the methods of digital research and data analysis, but also on best practices for the scientific uses of data. In spite of a certain humanistic bias towards data based on written sources, GIS and geodata are not being ousted from this conversation and the HTA community ought to get involved and – above all – take their cues from it. Beyond the respective scientific communities, public institutions such as municipal agencies rely increasingly on GIS resources for urban planning as well as heritage management and state

33 The Summer School "Hacking Mühlhausen. Digitale Sozialtopographie einer spätmittelalterlichen Stadt" (<https://www.uni-muenster.de/Staedtegeschichte/veranstaltungen/ZusVerIStG.html> (accessed 21.012025) was a cooperation between the IStG (Daniel Stracke and Anna-Lena Schumacher) and the University of Münster/Department of History (Colin Arnaud). I am grateful to Anna-Lena for her support and to Colin for taking the initiative and the lead in much of the planning of this adventure!

34 Scans of the sources were generously supplied by Stadtarchiv (Municipal Archives) Mühlhausen in Thüringen: StadtA Mühlhausen, 10-EE, Nr. 3, vol. 1 & 2; StadtA Mühlhausen, 10-Auf N, Nr. 1.

35 Schloms, Stracke & Wittmann, *Deutscher Historischer Städteatlas 6: Mühlhausen/Th.*, plate 1.1.

36 See Arnaud & Stracke, *Juden in Mühlhausen, Mühlhäuser Beiträge*[forthcoming].

37 In methods of spatial analysis, archaeologists are well advanced and in employ GIS in fruitful ways, even in exploring new approaches to comparative urbanism, see Benjamin Vis, *Cities made of boundaries. Mapping Social Life in Urban Form*, London 2018. See also Lelo, *Analysing spatial relationships*.

agencies increasingly adopt data-based strategies of eGovernment for all kinds of processes. GIS application is being taught in university courses and even school projects introduce basic geospatial knowledge, clearly making this technology even more relevant for the future. Also, the ICHT Atlas Working Group has recognised GIS as the fundamental technology for future HTA production.

The opportunities of the digital media revolution begin when we think of the world as „data-driven“, i.e. one in which the use, re-use, change, exchange and adaption of data is the central paradigm. Producing, pooling, and providing HTA data in forms that are usable and compatible will make the project results more useful for research and for the public.

Beyond the “sz” and “ß” – Data Standards for the HTA projects

Even after the print revolution had progressed beyond the wooden blockbook with the use of movable types, the early products of the medieval printing press were designed specifically to look like manuscripts. Printed books came with elaborate initials as well as variants for each letter, abbreviations, and ligatures to imitate the form of those publications that had moulded contemporary book buyers' expectations and that still dominated the market. Early prints were just as difficult to read as any manuscript, because simplification and standardisation was accomplished only over time. The analogy to the HTAs is a plain one; although it has been argued above, that a uniform style in the printed 1:2,500 Main Map can be dispensed with, the data-driven same approach does in fact call for standardisation in certain other ways in order to realise the full potential of the geodata, especially for comparative studies.

Analytic procedures such as measuring areas and distances as well as all kinds of statistical operations are a strong suit with GIS. Important to achieving comparability between HTA Main Map datasets for different towns are the methods of geodata production.³⁸ The two main operations in data processing cartographers have to perform in the GIS, – georeferencing and vectorising –, therefore, determine the accuracy of the data, and therefore merit a closer look. Georeferencing is a transformation of the original map image (i.e. the scan of the map uploaded) using exact modern survey data so that each point of the historic map is endowed with exact geographic coordinates. In georeferencing, there a lot of variables impacting the quality of the data: the general technique of aligning the historic maps (e.g. using their own grid system), the number of reference points relative to the size of the area, the clustering of the reference points over the area, the exact positioning of the points on the lines, and finally, the transformation algorithm working on the map image in between the reference points. Vectorisation is hardly more straightforward: the scale at which the outlines of buildings, streets and water courses on the historic survey maps are traced in the GIS has an influence on the accuracy of the digital vector model created. The larger the scale, the more exact the nodes can be placed on the ink lines of the original, and the more details of their depiction can be included. Vectorising a 1:500 plan at a scale of 1:2,500 will invariably result in the loss of smaller objects as well as architectural features in larger buildings such as rounded corners, ledges, columns, and so on. Therefore, variation in georeferencing and vectorising procedures may cause deviations in the localisation of topographic elements, their size/area and their shapes in the digital model of the town plan HTA cartographers build up in the GIS. These may lead to discrepancies in the results when researchers take their measurements in and derive their visualisations if different methods were used for the datasets.

As a general rule, analysis of data is limited to the properties embedded in the data structure. In the vectorisation process, the individual geofeatures, distinguished by a unique identifier, are to be classified and arranged on layers. Basic comparative analysis of geodata from different HTA projects is possible as long as information relating to the same content matter is arranged on corresponding layers in the GIS. As long as the data for the town layout, contourlines (as

38 See Czaja & Golba, Städteatlanten und GIS.

common in German HTAs), social data (found in Scandinavian HTA maps), and reconstructions (added in British and French HTAs) are stored on separate layers, they can be included in the analysis, or left out. If plot measurements are to be taken and analysed on the basis of the data, each plot boundary needs to be modelled as an individual polygon on the plot layer. The same is true for each object representing a building on the respective layer. Is this criterion fulfilled for both feature classes, not only plot sizes and built-up areas can be calculated, but the two layers can be related to each other and the building-to-plot ratio calculated. However, is the ground plan simply redrawn as in a map, i.e. without distinguishing the lines as representing the boundaries of buildings or of plots, such operations are impossible. For this reason, cartographers responsible for the production of geodata and researchers building analyses on their results need to closely work together right from the beginning so that the data enables all the analytical functions wanted to answer the research questions. Ideally, the data structure complies to the needs of researchers of all relevant academic disciplines and is made transparent for all the HTA projects to use. For truly achieving comprehensive comparability between Main Map datasets across the HTA community, the data structure and the level of data accuracy need to be the same and, hence, the methods of geodata production. Other factors, though, still need to be taken into consideration: variation in the cartographic source material and averse local conditions in some towns. Using a grid system already incorporated in the historic survey maps is certainly an ideal for georeferencing, but only few (and relatively late) maps have them. In many towns, the massive transformation of the townscape over time makes it very difficult to find persistent structures to be used as reference points for this procedure, because few historic buildings have survived destruction and rebuilding cycles. As with other types of historic evidence, inconsistencies in the sources and ambiguities in their readings are challenges also to the editors of cartographic records in the HTA projects. For obvious cartographic errors, unclear changes in the drawing, missing information due to subsequent corruption of the map (faded or smeared ink, bleaching, staining, holes in the paper), and other cases require standard editorial ways to communicate to the users that such issues may bias their interpretations.

The conceptual diversity and vagueness of source terms as well as the delimitation of historical phenomena that arise in the process are quite typical problems in the growing academic fields of 'Digital Humanities' and 'Digital History' where source evidence needs to be transposed into machine-readable data. Researchers in their studies have acquired knowledge about the phenomena they are likely to encounter in historic sources. Parts of this 'domain knowledge' may even derive from everyday knowledge we need to navigate the world. It is no big leap that the words "graveyard", "cemetery", "church yard" and "burial ground" all refer to places where people customarily dispose of the bodies of deceased members of their community. In fact, all these terms may in different texts be used for the one and the same place of this category. In other contexts, other terms may be used (e.g. cimiterium, Gottesacker etc.) and they may have different connotations. Computers, on the other hand, for lack of an everyday life, burial customs, and hands-on experience would be at a loss when standing in front of a neon sign saying 'GRAVEYARD – BURY THE DEAD HERE' – and asked to find a 'cemetery'. If, however, on entering even the corrupted form 'cemetery' into a search engine a computer presents you with correct hits comprising all different terms used for this concept, someone has gone the extra mile of teaching it semantics. Maps present the same problems. HTA cartographers have, for example, treated buildings very differently. Printed Main Map³⁹ legends show various categories: some use simply one all-inclusive class 'building', others differentiate buildings by building materials (wood, brick, stone), by their ownership or usage (private, ecclesiastical, public), or by their functions (habitation, economic, defence, worship, others). In printed maps, there is usually little room for supplying information as to where these categories

39 For Main Map 1:2,500 samples studied, see above.

are taken from and how they are defined. Moreover, categories are rarely straightforward or unambiguous: Is a monastic convent a ‘public building’, for example? The very word ‘cloister’ seems to suggest otherwise, but convents are well-known to have been the site of business transactions between worldly persons, and even reformed female monastic institutions with sisters strictly confined to the monastic enclosure are reported to have been visited frequently and extensively by laymen. Ambiguity pervades urban spaces in many instances and forms. This may not be much of a problem when comparing just two towns, but problems will get out of hand if computers are to assist with the analysis of multiple datasets.

As a remedy, ‘domain ontologies’ provide words with synonyms, terms with definitions, concepts with connections and semantic fields with hierarchies in order to structure the knowledge of a domain so that a common understanding about it may be shared. Such tools make communication possible between people, but also between people and machines, and even among machines. Ontologies are put into place so as to overcome the problem of implicit knowledge by making the conceptualisation of the world explicit. They are helpful not only for avoiding ambiguity in academic communication, but also make data accessible and allow for data sharing and system interoperability in the Semantic Web.⁴⁰ As a first attempt to describe the specific domain the HTA projects are dealing with, the project “Historical Ontology of Urban Spaces (HOUSE)” at the Polish Academy of Sciences in Warsaw⁴¹ used the urban landscape of present day Warsaw as a starting point of their descriptions, working their way back in time. Extending this work geographically to other areas and typologically to other towns remains a challenge, however.⁴² The goal of creating an ontology that can describe the phenomenology of historical urban spaces for all European towns to be implemented in the structure of HTA geodata in the future is a distant mirage that may yet turn out to be an illusion. Granularity and research questions may be the keys to success in building a common ontology that works to improve the comparability of digital spatial data and support future analytical studies.

When, for whatever reasons, uniformity cannot be achieved in HTA geodata production, transparency is needed as to what standards apply to a particular data set. This is achieved by adding to the geodata descriptive metadata. Appropriate metadata would need to contain information about the origins of the geodata, their versions, copyrights, production methods, internal structure, the sources used, and perhaps others, standardised in a separate metadata plan. Metadata, too, ought to come in forms making them readable by humans and machines alike, as for example are bibliographical metadata provided by libraries in their online catalogues. These enable the user to understand what media the institution has in store pertaining to one particular topic and where to find them.

Digital Shelves, Shelfmarks, and Libraries – Changing ways of collecting and storing research data

40 Linková, Nedbal & Rimnac, *Building Ontologies for GIS*. (https://www.researchgate.net/publication/266219565_Building_Ontologies_for_GIS [accessed 21.012025]).

41 See: <https://atlas.iopan.edu.pl/gis/urbanonto/> (accessed 21.012025). The project is supervised by Prof. IH PAN, Dr. hab. Marek Słoń in Warsaw.

42 See the Polish-German research project HiSMaComp – “Historical survey maps and the comparative study of the functionality and morphology of urban space. Standardisation – Digital processing – Research“ (<https://hismacomp.hypotheses.org/>) initiated by Roman Czaja (Uniwersytet Mikołaja Kopernika, Toruń) and Werner Freitag (Institut für vergleichende Städtegeschichte, Münster).

The library as an institution for storing knowledge pre-dates the media revolution initiated by the printing press, as is well-known. However, with falling prices and the commercialisation of the book market since its advent, book ownership, access to media, and also the library itself have changed to a certain degree. Since the Early Modern Age, libraries have had to deal with yet increasing numbers of media and needed to develop intricate procedures for storing and retrieving the individual volumes delivered into their care. Library stacks, shelves and volumes were marked to be systematically referenced and cross-referenced by ever more comprehensive catalogues. In this respect, the digital media revolution has new challenges in stock. The decentralised ways of information and data distribution the internet has to offer clearly is a 'blurse' – a blessing and a curse at the same time. Simplicity of upload and download as well as comparatively cheap storage in data clouds seem to solve the availability issue for good, also for the HTAs. Much less than an orderly library, though, the internet is like a vast pile of books – a mountain range of them – and only the most sophisticated search tools find anything, which may after all turn out to be the corrupted copy of a copy of some original work the author of which is long forgotten. For on the downside, the universal ability to publish, to copy, and to alter data multiplies the number of data outlets and may easily lead to confusion about the properties of 'published' datasets. Yet, the origins of data, sources, methods of production, publishing dates, versions, and copyrights are all necessary information if researchers are to use the data for their work. They depend on upholding scientific standards and themselves have an interest in presenting their research results as their own as well as in publishing their project data for future re-use.

For the HTA projects across Europe, it makes no sense to address the complex issues of storing and publishing their research data individually if they hold on to the common goal of delivering material for comparing past urban structures. If the possibilities of re-using research data for GIS-based studies are to be realised in full, a common effort is called for. Not only would the creation of multiple data outlets make finding suitable datasets difficult for any user; also, left to their own devices for inventing the wheel, not everyone may come up with the same roundish shape. And in this case, the goal is slightly more complex: to create a domain-specific (but cross-disciplinary) research data repository for the dissemination of project geodata, ensuring their long-term storage including data migration, and their permanent citability in other publications. It may come as a relief then, that with the HTA community in mind and for the benefit of comparative urban research at large, a 'digital library' is already under construction, a repository for the valuable geodata produced by the European HTA projects.

The IStG research data infrastructure is designed specifically with geodata in mind and hosted locally at the Center for Information Technology (CIT) of the University of Münster as one component. It runs on the software Open Geospatial Consortium's GeoServer software and uses GeoNode as a Content Management System for storing and presenting the data, making it available by download and standardised Web Services.⁴³ While the geoserver itself is up and running, there is still work to be done. To stick to the image, the bare brickwork of the building is already erected, but a library also needs a front desk controlling access to the media, shelves and desks as well as tools for research, and a comfortable lobby to welcome visitors. In times when data survival is threatened by the service deadlines of commercial companies, 'long-term sustainability' is much more than a topical buzzword. Therefore, the European research data

43 For more information see <https://geonode.org/>.

repository Zenodo is used as a second component by the IStG infrastructure to make sure that long-term storage of the valuable project data can be implemented.⁴⁴

Not only must the preservation and re-use of their research data be in the genuine interest of all HTA projects; research funding bodies are increasingly making plans for the sustainable preservation of research data a pre-requisite for successful applications to their programmes and so a suitable infrastructure comes in handy.

The system of ‘digital shelfmarks’ for retrieving the datasets from the vaults of the virtual library stacks is in place and, for obvious benefits, popular in academic publishing on the web already – the Digital Object Identifier (DOI).⁴⁵ The DOI is a unique code allocated to a specific digital publication on request by certified agencies, one of which is the University Library in Münster, in exchange for a defined set of metadata about the publication. This code, added to the dataset, may then be used to identify it in footnotes, bibliographies and other forms of annotations to find, reference and quote the work unambiguously and in accordance with basic academic conventions. This way, the HTA basic research geodata will be published in accordance with the ‘FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship’ – Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Re-use⁴⁶ – as useful, sustainable digital assets. While the geodata repository will offer a great service for the HTA projects, there is still a need for cooperation: On the practical side, uploading the data will be easy enough a procedure, but on doing so, the appropriate metadata need to be supplied by the projects. It is a minimal amount of work and well worth the effort. This way, anyone choosing to use the datasets will know exactly what to find in them, who has used what means to created them, and what he or she can and is allowed to do with them.

Such an infrastructure is not a stand-alone project, or shouldn’t be, as it shares many challenges with others. In Germany, a national research data infrastructure (*Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur*, NFDI)⁴⁷ is currently being established by the federal research funding body, the *Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft* (DFG). Its task is to create the conditions for decentralised project data from science and research to be systematically treated as an important resource and accessed, interlinked and made usable in the long term. Within this initiative, the NFDI Consortium ‘4memory’ wants to address the special characteristics of historical research data and the challenges these poses for data use and interoperability. Organisationally, the aim is to facilitate exchange and provide networking opportunities between researchers, memory institutions (archives, libraries, museums and collections), and information infrastructures.⁴⁸ The IStG has been accepted as a participant to this consortium. Although relatively small in the conglomerate of co-applicants, partners, and participants, the Institute's contribution to the group is nevertheless perceived as significant. This is because, on the one hand, with the geodata repository project it is building a relevant infrastructure for historical research data. On the other hand, with geodata, its efforts are focused a type of data so far under-represented and in need of standardisation. This way, the needs of the HTA projects

44 At present the storage policy is to retain the data uploaded “ for the lifetime of the repository”, currently the lifetime of the CERN laboratory (at least 20 years) see <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>.

45 For details, see: <https://www.doi.org/>. The DOI is already being used in footnotes no. 5 and 39 of this article!

46 <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> (accessed 21.01.2025).

47 <https://www.nfdi.de/> (accessed 21.01.2025).

48 For more information see <https://4memory.de> (accessed 21.01.2025); <https://www.nfdi.de/en-gb> (accessed 21.01.2025).

are being heard and standards to enable the usability and interoperability are carried into the international HTA community.

Conclusion

In the wake of the digital media revolution, many aspects of the work on Historic Towns Atlases have changed, and many still will. Meanwhile, the goals they have been called into being some 50 years ago, should remain the same: (1) conducting basic research for the topographical history of urban settlements, (2) providing material in standardised forms and formats to allow for comparisons, (3) making the material accessible in the long run as a lasting resource for urban studies. It has been tried to show that in times in which research is increasingly being conducted based on the calculating capabilities of the computer, this is best achieved by following a 'data-driven approach'. This means not to focus on the visualisation side of print and online maps only, but on producing geodata as basic research to, yes, print maps, but also to benefit other projects by making the data re-usable. This involves not only the introductions of new – data and metadata – standards, but also building and using a digital publication infrastructure, an HTA Geodata Repository.

The step towards a 'research data consciousness' in the scientific community and towards a culture that, in addition to data production, also plans the provision of basic data for interdisciplinary, transnational and comparative research, is greater than expected. So far, HTA projects using GIS do so without pursuing common data strategies and the international community faces an imminent fragmentation of effort with the unsolved technological issues. There is a risk of incompatible results, low public profile, and inefficiency. The principle goal of the European HTA projects, to create a sound basis for comparative research is in danger of being jeopardized and their work may be neglected as a source of historical topographical information. A comparable output is vital to conduct research across national borders and helps to understand the common roots, chronological phases and formative processes which affected towns all over Europe. At present, impressed with the opportunities of internet publishing and an eye mainly on the availability issue, the HTA projects tend to go for any online solution – the quicker it is achieved, the better. This mentality, however, needs to change. HTA projects must re-emphasise the idea of producing map data as fundamental research and that they lay the foundations on which other studies can and should be based. The establishment of data standards is crucial indeed, as these technical processes of data production will invariably, and fundamentally influence the results that can be achieved by employing HTA geodata in research, i.e. their usability.⁴⁹

Technical change has affected the atlas work before – just think of digital drawing, imaging, and printing technologies – and it will keep on doing so. Technical progress is hard to predict and not linear; digital progress is fast. We are still very much in the middle of the digital revolution, and there are many moving parts. Yet, many colleagues have been searching, probing, and experimenting, and together the HTA projects have gained a lot of understanding, since Katalin Szende, back in 2012, initiated a first workshop in Budapest to discuss the digital challenge and pathways into the future of the HTAs. Now, the projects are and will be creating geodata, at least for the foreseeable future. From this data, we print our HTAs – they are our key product. The future of the print HTAs beyond the current digital media revolution is a question of relevance: The print atlases, where they exist, are in most cases in demand, their audience often being – and this attractiveness is a compliment – lay people interested in their home town and local historians. Moreover, untouched by academic trends and scientific 'turns', this audience retains a lively interest in the history of the urban landscape, asking about the history and spatial development of 'their' town with a genuine appetite for fact-checked,

⁴⁹ The Digital Standards Group initiated by Daniel Stracke as a sub committee to the Atlas Working Group, now headed by Niklas Alt, Marburg, is step by step filling the gaps.

reliable information. On the academic side, however, the geodata are the relevant product. Hence, especially with new HTA projects, it is quite uncertain if the production of a print atlas is still a goal and possible, in the long run. With the LUXATLAS, the first purely digital project has been born and progressed well beyond infancy. While the lack of a print series is for many reasons a loss, there is no need to despair in this data-driven world. The data produced in the project is, after all, re-usable so that printing a map from the geodata is always an option, even if this is not part of the original plan and funding application.

But isn't all this too much hassle – working on abstract standards and building an infrastructure for the relatively small HTA community with a yearly output of perhaps between ten and twenty printed atlas publications? Do we need to think the future that big? To answer in the affirmative, a brief look back on the HTA work, and ahead into current developments in informatics may suffice. Producing the geodata as a basis for the atlases, especially processing the cadastral survey maps for the 1:2,500 Main Map is a time- and labour-intensive task that can take a highly skilled cartographer months to complete – depending on the size and building density of the town. Experimental work on solutions to carry out at least parts of the vectorising process (semi-)automatically has been underway for some time and may become the starting point for further research.⁵⁰ It seems like it won't be long, before the HTA work can be enormously facilitated and speeded up by the use of algorithms that are frequently subsumed under the heading 'artificial intelligence'. The goal, of course cannot be to put the project cartographers out of work, on the contrary. More efficient geodata production methods will, on the one hand, allow them time to use the geodata for producing developmental and thematic maps to benefit the research aspect of the projects and to quickly broaden the data basis which also will put research results on more stable footing. The increasing amount of data to be produced by the HTA community, but also the possibility of combining their work with geodata produced in other fields of urban studies, is bound to make the effort of creating a suitable infrastructure worthwhile. This way, the positive potential of the digital media revolution would indeed be realised to the benefit of historical urban studies in general and the HTA community especially.

50 A cooperation of IStG with the Computer Vision and Machine Learning Systems Group of the Institute for Computer Science at the University of Münster yielded promising results, see the master's thesis by Mhd. Suffian Zaabalawi "Automated vectorization of historical maps using state-of-the-art Computer Vision techniques", supervised by Jun.-Prof. Benjamin Risse, represents a major step in this direction. The results of the work based on this material were presented as a poster presentation at the Digital Humanities Day (DH@WWU2020 "DH connected"). See also: [Risse/Zaabalawi: Automatische Vektorisierung](#).

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